

**Fall Prevention Error-Administration of Poor Communication leading to Fall
and Potential Injury.**

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Abstract

The healthcare administration sector regularly witnesses a huge drop in patient outcomes due to the oversights that happen at the functional level. Among those, fall prevention errors, administration of poor communication leading to fall and potential injury or even deaths of in-patients, is an issue that needs serious attention. Every year, nearly 1 million patients fall, “leading to over 250,000 injuries and approximately 11,000 deaths” (Li & Surineni, 2025, para.1). This case analysis will examine the problem of patient falls based on communication flaws and analyze the problems based on the incident of a 60-year-old woman whose monitoring was met with medical miscommunication in a research hospital. Furthermore, the paper will analyze its root causes, suggest a quality improvement framework, describe the roles of the stakeholders, lay out statistical tools, and analyze the effectiveness of the implementation strategies. This paper will also provide an approach to lower the occurrence of patient falls and enhance communication methods and training in the healthcare environment.

Introduction

Background of the Problem

In a recent study on patient falls, out of the 4,176 incidents reported, “79.0% were unwitnessed by nurses, and 8.7% occurred during direct nursing care” (Takase, 2022, para.14). This fact implies a serious lack of seamless communication or negligence among nurses or other providers and suggests how it can impact patient safety. These incidents occur mainly in older patients with communication disabilities. Also, there are existing gaps in staffing, appropriate skill mix, documentation, leadership, and equipment knowledge. Prompt administrative strategies including transparent communication and training can help activate fall prevention strategies.

Communication barriers can have debilitating consequences for patients, especially when clarity of instructions becomes a key factor for their health and well-being when admitted to a hospital. Patients who are aged, have cognitive problems, hearing issues, or those who have ailments like stroke have trouble processing information communicated and convey their needs. It has been found that such patients experience unprecedented falls as their needs are not met in the hospital. Healthcare professionals have documented that it was challenging to access patients who had problems with communication. It can be shown with the case study of a 60-year-old woman who was admitted to the Neuro-ICU after a cardiac arrest, which underlined the issue of failure to observe high fall risk patients and negligence to educate the family on fall prevention. After a few days, although she showed signs of improvement like responding to her name and following commands, the patient was assessed by a physical therapist who stated that the patient is at a high risk of falls due to poor balance and disorientation. During a routine cleaning procedure, the patient was on the recliner and her daughter was seated opposite. While the

Resident Nurse had to leave the room for a moment, she failed to instruct the bystander that the patient should not attempt to move. As could be seen from the video monitoring that recorded the incident, the patient tried to stand up, resulting in a fatal fall leading to several injuries, and paralysis down the neck.

Root Cause Analysis

The gaps that exist in the current system and their root causes should be analytically addressed in order to develop a framework for addressing them. The case of the 60-year-old patient who experienced a fall due to miscommunication can be analyzed further in the light of the data that was recorded while the patient was admitted. While the patient's functional status was reviewed before her fall, her balance findings were recorded to be to be poor and static (*Nurse Medical Malpractice Case Study with Risk Management Strategies*, 2024, para.4). It was also found that she was confused about the location and has poor safety awareness. Nursing documentation also highlighted that the patient was educated on fall prevention measures, which were later found to be ineffective.

This incident seems to be the result of multiple flaws. Although the underlying risks associated with ageism are quite evident, the hospital staff seemed to have overlooked them and provided insufficient fall prevention education. Various other cases also illustrate that there is no proper knowledge transfer, motivation, or awareness given by the caregivers to the patients or their families to engage in fall prevention behaviors. There is very little training in this regard as these incidents are taken for granted that the older people get limited opportunities to practice these fall prevention acts. Just as in the case of the 60-year-old woman, an unfamiliarity of the environment may prevent such older ones from seeking help at appropriate times. Although it is stated that the patient is educated on fall prevention, there are cases where such education

becomes “sporadic or inconsistent” (Hill et al., 2024, para.5). The staff often fails to give clear instructions to the patient, which may spur unprecedented falls. In addition, it is also found that the staff lacks the training to be good listeners who can acknowledge and support patient needs, leading to communication gaps.

Also, sometimes patients are not properly instructed on how to use the safety assistance equipment like bedside communication board. Most of the time, instructions are given to patients excluding their family from such conversations. Although the family members know their parents better than the providers, their perspectives are neglected when the doctors and nurses provide instructions on health and safety. The lack of motivation and support from the family in providing valid fall prevention measures can also be a result of incompetent safety instructions that may lead to patient falls in hospitals.

An underlying root cause of falls due to communication issues is staff shortages and insufficient staff-to-resident ratios. In a survey, one of the nurses responded thus: “You have only two nurses and one care assistant at night, so it is hard to be eyes everywhere and in every room” (Albasha et al., 2024, para.20). This insufficiency in staffing can affect the quality of communication as there are problems like workload, staff movement, and time constraints. In addition, new staff members lack the expertise or experience to handle people with dementia or deviant behaviors even if they have fresh knowledge. This will in turn increase the workload of senior nurses, resulting in poor quality delivery of their services including communication with patients. The strategies that are supposed to raise the quality like official staff meetings are noted to be ineffective.

Patient-related-factors also affect communication. Patients may lack the insight to receive the instructions to avoid falls. For instance, due to lack of proper understanding, patients may fall

in “using the call bell, not waiting for assistance, etc.” (Heng et al., 2022, para.18). This can be regarded as a lack of proper engagement with fall prevention education. Also, it was found that “overcrowdedness and total amount of falls were positively and very strongly correlated” ($r=0.875$, $p<0.001$) (Stathopoulos et al., 2021, para.1). Essentially, when the number of patients is more, it is hard for the nursing staff to manage all of their needs simultaneously, which may cause oversights that can trigger patient falls. Also, inconsistencies in visual tools increases communication gaps. For instance, one site may indicate patient fall through a falling leaf while another uses high-risk, low-risk labels. This apparent difference in what is intended to be conveyed hinders hassle-free communication. Thus, the causal factors and root causes that may affect communication failures catalyzing patient falls may range from insufficient staffing, inadequate training, lack of patient engagement, and inconsistent displays of visual guidelines as shown in the Fishbone Diagram below (Figure 1).

**Figure 1: Fishbone Diagram-
Fall Prevention Error due to Administration of Poor
Communication resulting in falls and potential injury**

Methods / Quality Improvement Framework

Various strategies for fall prevention errors still widely exist, and the quality of patient care is compromised due to a number of reasons rooted in communication issues, which may result in prolonged hospital stays or more complications due to patient falls. These causes should be systematically studied and addressed so that communication between nurses and patients can be enhanced to lower the rates of patient falls in hospitals. I will be using the Six Sigma Framework also known as DMAIC to address the issue of communication based on fall prevention errors in hospitals. The goal of this quality improvement framework is to enhance communication interventions like addressing inadequacy in staffing, training, and communication to create a safe environment for patients.

Studies suggest up to one million falls occur in hospitals in the United States of America annually (Woltsche, 2022, para.1). Addressing this deep rooted issue requires well-planned procedures. The first step is to measure and determine baseline data of miscommunication problems based on the age, sex, potential causes for fall, time of fall, and patient-level risk for fall. It is vital to delve deeper into all possible causes for fall, particularly communication related issues; such detailed research records that while patient related factors are around 37.5%, staff and communication factors come around 17.9% (Lakbala, 2024, para.12). The fact that patient falls due to communication issues mostly occur for vulnerable older adults population underlines the importance of having systematic guidelines for them, educating them appropriately, and communicating every meticulous instruction to them to prevent falls. Accordingly, strategies to reduce falls can be broadly classified as “environmental measures and physical protection (29.4%), identifying, and displaying the causes of risk (23.5%), education (21.6%)..., and

supervision and monitoring (11.8%)” (Lakbala, 2024, para.13). A systematic framework for improving the current scenario should be planned by addressing flaws and underlying issues.

Among certain possibilities to reduce patient falls due to miscommunication, the primary focus area should be to better enhance the interventions in patient and nurse education training. Accordingly, the nurse would be offered practical training sessions with real life scenarios and guidance on the risk of falls and proper interventions. For example, a study discovered that nurses who have been educated on interventions like “assistive mobilization like support belts” (Garcia et al., 2021, para.21). Also, they should be instructed to increase vigilance during fall prone days like that of increased medication, meal time, etc. In addition, patients should be given awareness of fall risks and encourage them to communicate their needs effectively before attempting movement on their own. For instance, patient education programs like Safe Recovery Program facilitate a positive environment to support fall prevention. Under this framework, thorough guidance can be given on how to use assistive technologies like bed alarms or walking aids, bringing awareness lessons through visual aids like multimedia to enhance patient engagement, ensuring that bystanders are aware of the strategies for prevention.

It is also imperative to improve the web of communication between staff members so that no patient goes unmonitored at no instances so that video monitoring facilities are best used to enhance patient monitoring. It is important to ensure an interdisciplinary approach where there is tight communication between members of the healthcare team. In order to avoid oversight or problems due to lack of proper training and skills, inexperienced staff should always be guided and monitored by senior staff members so that any negligence of fall instances can be avoided. Communication as well as collaboration on handling video monitoring systems is a mandatory aspect of fall prevention strategy.

Certain control methods that could be implemented to realize the improvement framework in practical ways. At the outset, a portable video monitoring system and centralized video monitoring which could offer close monitoring facilities should be installed so that fall-prone patients can be watched more closely and constantly. As per studies, “video monitoring has shown a statistical reduction from 6.34 to 5.10 falls per 1000 patient-days” (Woltsche, 2022, para.8). With the help of these monitoring systems it will allow the nurses to be proactively intervening in situations to prevent falls. Also, the integration of latest technology like the use of “human sized mobile platforms like the Adaptive Robotic Nursing Assistant” can be helpful in preventing patient fall by strengthening the patient's gait (Li & Surineni, 2025). Sensors can be integrated into shoes, watches, hospital gowns, and hospital furniture, combined with smartphone technology to further trigger alarms and notify staff so that preventive interventions can be made during the right timing (Li & Surineni, 2025). Such nonverbal, automated forms of communication should be implemented to enhance the effectiveness of reducing patient falls.

Stakeholders/Team Project Members

To execute the control measures suggested, a multidisciplinary team of nurses, facilitating staff, patients, physicians, family members, and therapists should be formed. This group will help develop an intricate support system that can discuss and execute well-planned fall prevention methods. Patients and their family members are primary stakeholders as their personalized needs provide insights into planning strategies so that the communication problems can be analyzed through various dimensions. The healthcare team is responsible for making personalized fall prevention plans for patients according to their needs and implementing them effectively.

Likewise, having an efficient project team that can fortify communication is essential for the successful achievement of goals in reducing patient falls in every stage passing through planning, implementation, and evaluation of strategies. Firstly, following the Six Sigma Model, a senior executive, called the project champion, should be given charge. Project champions can enhance and support fall prevention. They also act as a bridge between the team and leadership to facilitate the project of fall prevention strategies to enhance communication. Then, a project team of interdisciplinary experts consisting of doctors, therapists, and nurses can be identified so that they can be responsible for collecting data, analysis of execution strategies. Also, there should be a team of skilled individuals who have expertise in collecting data, evaluating and examining them. These data analysts should be able to analyze data and find resolutions through a comprehensive examination of the trends of patient fall in hospitals. Individuals in the healthcare team like nurses or department heads are process owners of the project team who collaborates with the team and identifies areas of improvement. Ultimately, fall prevention plans also require an efficient project manager who can work on resource allocation, fosters effective communication among the project team members, and ensure deadlines regarding fall prevention measures are met. To drive every project process and to maintain the balance of Six Sigma guidelines for success of fall prevention interventions, experts called Master Black belts aid in fine-tuning them. They coach the project team and resolve complex issues that may arise during the projects' execution across the entire organization. The stakeholders and the project team together can collaboratively work on implementing adequate strategies in systematic ways to materialize effective communication interventions.

Statistical/Analysis Tools

There are many statistical tools which can be beneficial in measuring and examining the results of quality improvement projects to strengthen communication aspects. Firstly, control charts are such tools that can help in monitoring and analyzing fall prevention strategies. The nurses and the team can follow up the rates of fall per 1,000 bed days on the ward and examine the impact of the strategies over time. The Control Chart would help to closely monitor the data gathered and study the cause of differences and issues in fall rates during a time period. When examining these issues using systematic PDSA cycles, the team can implement strategies like effective training, identifying patients with high fall risks etc. and bring changes in fall services by executing shifts that can result in reduction of falls in patients. In addition, there is user-friendly statistical analysis software for Fall Prevention Protocol that allows a follow up of the influence of changes made to the existing programs. Particularly, this application can alleviate miscommunication issues by defining objectives clearly, eliminating the waiting period and enhancing the effectiveness of communication. In addition, electronic analysis tools like controlled interrupted time series can be used in predicting fall risks based on patient's conditions and nurses' responses; this helps to target risk-prone patients with customized interventions like that of communication and education rather than applying universal fall prevention strategies.

Results and Future Outcomes

To evaluate the effectiveness and capability of fall prevention solutions, it is vital to analyze implementation strategies. As a prospective healthcare administrator, I would implement customized strategies like Patient Fall Prevention Tool Kits to evaluate how far the communication enhancement strategies are useful in achieving our goal. For instance, it is ideal

to utilize Fall Tailoring Interventions for Patient Safety Toolkit, which is a personalized prevention plan that works consistently, and seems to have resulted in “25% fall reduction in hospital settings” (Dykes et al., 2024, para.6). Also, I would execute strategies for improving staff education, quality management strategies such as posting fall rates or having staff huddles after a fall event can also be implemented to prevent falls. With specifically defined strategies, it is important to regularly monitor and evaluate their effectiveness so that appropriate changes can be made to meet the goals.

The implemented strategies can also be measured and reported in predetermined ways by analyzing patient safety and outcomes. A communication tool called SBAR can be employed to measure the effectiveness of implemented strategies. This tool functions well in documenting effectiveness of communication between nurses and patients by ensuring their improvement through training and education and enhancing the competencies of the nurses. It is vital to introduce future studies on effective techniques so that updated strategies on follow up measures can be implemented.

Conclusion

Overall, this case analysis paper offers a profound view into the issue of fall prevention errors in relation to poor communication. The example of the case study illustrates how communication gaps are often neglected in the case of patient falls but how they are most avoidable causes of patient falls if right care is given. Examining the root cause analysis of the issue, it is evident that factors like number of staff, nurse training, patient orientation are those that affect communication. However, the quality improvement framework, strategic planning and statistical tools suggested in the case analysis can effectively reduce patient falls due to communication gaps.

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